

TRANSLATION OF CULTURAL ELEMENTS IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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Abstract: This article addresses the challenge of translating cultural-specific elements, recognized as one of the most complex issues in translation studies. The research explores this problem within the context of translation methodology, emphasizing the importance of analyzing existing (foreign) translation solutions to identify potential errors and shortcomings. This approach contributes to the development of students' critical thinking, fostering an awareness of the need to build a foundation of extra linguistic knowledge for the sake of professional competence.

Keywords: cultural-specific elements; culturally marked lexicon; intercultural competence; intercultural adaptation; transcription; transliteration; calque; descriptive translation.

In the context of translating texts across genres, translators grapple with culturally specific elements, posing a complex challenge. This challenge persists in training translation students. Our proposed solution involves an integrated approach. On one hand, developing students' intercultural competence is essential, providing background knowledge about the language's country in academic subjects and extracurricular contexts. On the other hand, teaching the translation of cultural elements in theory and practice classes is crucial.

In these sessions, students learn about culturally marked vocabulary and the challenges of intercultural adaptation when using another language. They acquire fundamental methods for conveying cultural elements, a vital aspect of their future professional work. Additionally, students gain basic knowledge necessary for successful translation. Another critical aspect is enhancing students' skills in researching and using internet resources, online dictionaries, etc., which significantly aids task completion and reduces the risk of translation errors.

Within translation didactics, analyzing existing translation solutions and learning from others' mistakes is essential in preventing students' errors. This article delves into these aspects, emphasizing their significance in the educational process for translation students. Before exploring errors in regional studies translation, let's outline theoretical principles from scientific literature. Two main approaches to defining elements exist: translation and regional studies. We follow the approach of S. Vlahov and S. Florin, considering elements as words and phrases expressing national and temporal characteristics. Their classification considers thematic, local, and temporal features. [1.p.59-88]

Techniques for translating elements include transcription, transliteration, tracing, descriptive translation, and transformational translation. These methods are applied in analyzing student translations from German to Russian, encompassing ethnographic, everyday, art and cultural, as well as socio-political elements. It's noteworthy that various researchers provide diverse classifications of elements. The focus of this work should be on translation examples using the mentioned methods to assess their effectiveness and correctness.

When analyzing options for translating elements, one should pay attention to the fact that the translator is faced not only with the belonging of elements to a certain area of foreign cultural reality but also with "mastered" elements that are already present in the Russian language [2]. In the proposed translation options for Oktoberfest, the authors use various methods: transliteration (Oktoberfest), a combined method (Munich Beer Festival), descriptive translation (Annual beer festival "Oktoberfest"), as well as transliteration with tracing (Oktoberfest – Celebration October).

It is important to note that the second and third options allow you to preserve information about the object through a combination of transliteration and descriptive translation, while the fourth option, using tracing paper in brackets, does not contribute to a full understanding of the cultural elements.

Let's move on to the next episodic reality related to the carnival in Germany. Here, the translator has to choose the appropriate option, taking into account the different names of this holiday depending on the region. He must also consider that preparations begin in advance, in November, and the official start of the carnival season is announced in November [3]

Translation 1: Who needs a carnival in Rio de Janeiro when you can have it in Germany.

Translation 2: Who wants to go to the carnival in Rio de Janeiro neuro when you can celebrate it in Germany!

The first and second variants omit synonymous holiday names, losing important information.

Translation 3: Who needs a carnival in Rio de Janeiro, if the carnival, carnival and the eve of Lent can be celebrated in Germany!

Translation 4: Who needs Rio de Janeiro when you can celebrate the carnival, the eve of Lent and Carnival in Germany!

Texts 3 and 4 use synonyms for Karneval, corresponding to lexical units in Russian.

Note that in German the name of this tradition and its celebration are borrowed from the Latin language. The history of the holiday is connected with the Roman Empire. For example, German-language sources mention two possible origins of the carnival, related to the Christian tradition of the beginning of Lent and the secular custom of celebrating the opening of shipping. Karneval - [ital. Carnevale] may occur from mlat. carnevale (-levare) = Fleischwegnahme (during fasting) or mlat. carrus navalis = Schiffskarren, Schiff auf Rädern (for spring parades marking the opening of shipping) with an analogy to lat. carne vale = Fleisch, lebe wohl!] [4].

In German culture, this holiday is associated with church tradition and has its own peculiarities. Russian culture also has this tradition with its own characteristics and name.

The logic of the authors of the third and fourth texts of the translation is obvious, which convey the realities of a similar translation, focused on the search for an analogy in their culture, close to the foreign reality and understandable to the reader. This avoids gaps in the text of the translation, but it loses its "exoticity". [5, pp. 17-21]. In conclusion, this analytical approach in translation classes fosters the development of students' critical thinking and underscores the importance of building extra linguistic knowledge for the formation of professional competence.

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